

THE USAGE OF METAPHOR IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK: A COMPARATIVE LINGUISTIC ANALYSIS

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Annotation. *This study examines the concept of metaphor in English and Uzbek linguistics, focusing on its types, functions, and cultural significance. Traditionally regarded as a literary device, metaphor is now considered an essential mechanism of human cognition and communication. The research analyzes metaphorical expressions found in literary works, idioms, and everyday speech in both languages. It highlights the similarities and differences in the use of metaphors, demonstrating how cultural and linguistic factors influence figurative meaning. The study also distinguishes metaphor from simile and explains the role of metaphor in expressing abstract ideas, emotions, and human experiences. Through comparative analysis, the research contributes to a deeper understanding of metaphor as both a linguistic and cognitive phenomenon.*

Key words: *Metaphor, figurative meaning, cognitive linguistics, simile, imagery, symbolism, English linguistics, Uzbek linguistics, figurative language, literary device.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu tadqiqot ingliz va o'zbek tilshunosligida metafora tushunchasini, uning turlari, funksiyalari hamda madaniy ahamiyatini o'rganadi. An'anaviy ravishda metafora adabiy vosita sifatida qaralgan bo'lsa, zamonaviy tilshunoslikda u inson tafakkuri va muloqotining muhim mexanizmi sifatida talqin qilinadi. Tadqiqotda badiiy asarlar, iboralar va kundalik nutqda uchraydigan metaforik ifodalar tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, ingliz va o'zbek tillaridagi metaforalarning o'xshash hamda farqli jihatlari ko'rsatilib, figurativ ma'noga madaniy va lingvistik omillarning ta'siri yoritiladi. Tadqiqot metafora va o'xshatishning farqlarini tushuntirib, metaforaning mavhum g'oyalari, hissiyotlar va inson tajribalarini ifodalashdagi rolini ochib beradi. Qiyosiy tahlil orqali metaforaning lingvistik va kognitiv hodisa sifatidagi mohiyatini chuqurroq anglashga hissa qo'shiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Metafora, ko'chma ma'no, kognitiv tilshunoslik, o'xshatish, obrazlilik, ramziylik, ingliz tilshunosligi, o'zbek tilshunosligi, badiiy til, adabiy vosita.*

Аннотация. *Данное исследование посвящено изучению метафоры в английском и узбекском языкознании, её типов, функций и культурного значения. Традиционно метафора рассматривалась как литературный приём, однако современная лингвистика рассматривает её как важный механизм человеческого мышления и коммуникации. В работе анализируются метафорические выражения, встречающиеся в художественной литературе, идиомах и повседневной речи обоих языков. Особое внимание уделяется сходствам и различиям в употреблении метафор, а также влиянию культурных и языковых факторов на переносное значение. Исследование также разграничивает понятия метафоры и сравнения, раскрывая роль метафоры в выражении абстрактных идей, эмоций и человеческого опыта. Сравнительный анализ способствует более глубокому пониманию метафоры как лингвистического и когнитивного явления.*

Ключевые слова: *Метафора, переносное значение, когнитивная лингвистика, сравнение, образность, символизм, английское языкознание, узбекское языкознание, художественный язык, литературный приём.*

Introduction

Metaphor is an important part of human language and cognitive thinking. Traditionally, it has been studied and used as a linguistic device in literary texts to create an imagery in the reader's mind as well as to improve expressiveness. However, scholars of this time consider metaphor not only as a literary ornament but also as the fundamental mechanism of human thought and creativity. According to George Lakoff and Mark Johnson, in their book *Metaphors We Live By*, metaphor shapes the way people form abstract ideas and structure their everyday experiences (1983).¹

In Uzbek linguistics, metaphor is considered a piece of figurative meaning (*ko'chma ma'no*) and studied alongside metonymy and synecdoche. While these figurative devices are universal in nature, their manifestations vary across languages and cultures, reflecting unique cognitive and linguistic patterns. Therefore, this study aims to analyze the types and functions of metaphors in English and Uzbek to identify differences and similarities. Clarifying their origin, functions, and cultural influence, we enter. It is different to have a complete understanding of the role of simile in these two languages. We will look at sources including literary works, proverbs, and idioms. By comparing these two linguistic traditions, the research seeks to contribute to a deeper understanding of metaphor and its usage.

METAPHOR IN ENGLISH

A metaphor is a figure of speech that highlights similarities for emphasis or symbolism by comparing two distinct things by saying that one is the other.² Although the compared aspects are not exactly the same, they are connected to foster a deeper comprehension or conjure up images. Metaphors use colourful, creative language to help communicate abstract ideas, feelings, or difficult topics. They are frequently employed to provide depth and expressiveness in speech, poetry, literature, and daily conversation. A metaphor strengthens the relationship between concepts by drawing a direct parallel, in contrast to a simile, which use like or as.

When we employ metaphor, we go beyond simple, logical comparison to an identification or fusion of two items, creating a new entity with traits from both: the voice is silk, not like silk. Making metaphors is seen by many critics as a way of thinking that predates or circumvents logic. Despite being prevalent on all levels and in all forms of language, metaphor is the basic language of poetry. Many of the words we use on a daily basis were once vibrant imagery, but they are now dead metaphors whose original meaning has faded. For instance, the term "daisy" is derived from an Old English phrase that means "day's eye." The ray-like appearance of the daisy, which opens and closes with the sun, is reminiscent of an eye that opens in the morning and closes at night.³ The expression time flies is also metaphorical, with time being identified with a bird. A metaphor can serve a variety of purposes in poetry, ranging from highlighting straightforward similarities between objects to inspiring a wide range of ideas; it can be a minor component or the poem's main idea and dominant image. For instance, the intricate fundamental idea of one of Emily Dickinson's poems is the metaphor of an iron horse for a train, even though neither the iron horse nor the train appears in the poem. The poem's opening and last stanzas are:

I like to see it lap the Miles—

¹ Thorne, J. P. (1983). George Lakoff and Mark Johnson, *Metaphors we live by*. Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press, 1980

² Merriam Webster <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/metaphor>

³ Harper, Douglas. "Daisy." *Online Etymology Dictionary*, www.etymonline.com/word/daisy

And lick the Valleys up—
And stop to feed itself at Tanks—
And then—prodigious step

However, in songs, we can usually encounter unusual metaphorical phrases that can grab the attention of many. Lawrence W. Levine draws attention to a crucial contrast between various musical genres⁴. Traditional styles like hollers, work songs, field songs, and blues frequently convey their ideas more plainly, but many songs rely on vague metaphors and intricate symbols that enable unlimited interpretation. These genres, which particularly represent labour, adversity, and emotional difficulty, are firmly anchored in people's everyday realities. Because of this, their messages are typically understandable and don't need to be further examined. According to Levine's theory, meaningful art doesn't always rely on concealed symbolism; in many situations, honesty and simplicity can convey human truth just as well.

EXAMPLES FOR EVERY DAY LIFE

Examples from everyday life: "You are my sunshine." Someone is being compared to the sun in this instance. The earth receives a lot of light from the brilliant sunshine. This implies that the individual is extremely content and makes other people happy. "They were peas in a pod." Since peas in a pod are typically quite close to one another, nothing can separate the individuals in this metaphor. It's a rollercoaster. Rollercoasters can be frightening, have a lot of twists and turns, and travel swiftly. This implies that life is fast-paced, has highs and lows, and occasionally can be a touch frightening. However, life can also be a lot of fun, much like a rollercoaster! It is important to distinguish between metaphors and similes. Similes establish a comparison between two distinct entities through the use of explicit markers such as “like” or “as,” whereas metaphors assert a direct equivalence by describing one entity as being another. This fundamental difference highlights the more implicit and interpretive nature of metaphorical language compared to the explicit comparative structure of similes.

METAPHOR IN UZBEK

Metaphor means “transfer.” The transfer of meaning based on the external similarity, shape, or internal characteristics of objects, things, and phenomena is called a metaphor. More often, metaphor is based on external similarity. In the method of metaphor, the transfer of a name occurs due to a relative similarity between objects and phenomena, such as their color, shape, or movement, where one takes the name of another with similar features. In this process, a general feature is preserved when the meaning is transferred.

For example, in the phrase “black intention,” the word “black” undergoes a transfer of meaning. When used alone, “black” simply denotes a color, but due to its association with negativity or evil, it metaphorically conveys a bad intention.

In particular, Aristotle used this term in a broader sense. In his work *Rhetoric*, he expressed the following idea: “Metaphor possesses a high degree of clarity, pleasantness, and expressive power; when used appropriately, it beautifies speech.”

Metaphors are commonly found in the following:

1. Parts of the human body (hand, foot, face, lips, teeth, shoulder).
2. Clothing and its parts (collar, hem).
3. Animals, birds, and insects (wing, tail, beak, horn).
4. Plants and their parts (root, branch).

⁴ Levine, L. W. (1993). *The unpredictable past: Explorations in American cultural history*. Oxford University Press.

5. Tools (spear, knife).

For example: “a house at the foot of the mountain,” “Our house is on the river bank.”

“Her eyebrows are like a bow, her eyelashes are arrows, her lips are buds, her teeth are pearls, her face is like the moon, her face is like a flower, she is like a fairy” — such beautiful expressions can mainly be found in Uzbek literature. This style of usage is characteristic of Uzbek poets and writers.

In words, there are two types of meaning: the first is literal meaning, and the second is figurative meaning. If we consider literal meaning, a word expresses the same meaning whether it appears alone or within a text. Such meaning is called the literal meaning of a word. However, if the meaning of a word when used alone differs from its meaning within a text, then the word is used in a figurative sense.

How can we determine whether a word is used literally or figuratively? The answer is simple: we consider the word in isolation. If the meaning remains the same both independently and within the text, it is literal; if it changes, then it is figurative.

This can be explained through examples. For instance, in the sentence “Do not have a cold intention, my friend,” the word “cold” when used alone refers to temperature related to air or water. However, in phrases like “cold intention,” “cold breath,” or “cold expression,” the word “cold” moves away from its literal meaning and is used figuratively.

Similarly, in the sentence “My stomach is full of you,” the word “full” when used alone refers to something physically filled. However, within the sentence, it conveys a different meaning, showing that the word is used figuratively. Thus, we learn that words can carry both literal and figurative meanings and how to distinguish between them.

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